

**INFORMATION ABOUT PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATORS/PROJECT DIRECTORS(PI/PD) and
co-PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATORS/co-PROJECT DIRECTORS**

Submit only ONE copy of this form for each PI/PD and co-PI/PD identified on the proposal. The form(s) should be attached to the original proposal as specified in GPG Section II.B. Submission of this information is voluntary and is not a precondition of award. This information will not be disclosed to external peer reviewers. **DO NOT INCLUDE THIS FORM WITH ANY OF THE OTHER COPIES OF YOUR PROPOSAL AS THIS MAY COMPROMISE THE CONFIDENTIALITY OF THE INFORMATION.**

PI/PD Name: Wendy K Warnick

Gender: Male Female
Ethnicity: (Choose one response) Hispanic or Latino Not Hispanic or Latino

Race:
(Select one or more)
 American Indian or Alaska Native
 Asian
 Black or African American
 Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander
 White

Disability Status:
(Select one or more)
 Hearing Impairment
 Visual Impairment
 Mobility/Orthopedic Impairment
 Other
 None

Citizenship: (Choose one) U.S. Citizen Permanent Resident Other non-U.S. Citizen

Check here if you do not wish to provide any or all of the above information (excluding PI/PD name):

REQUIRED: Check here if you are currently serving (or have previously served) as a PI, co-PI or PD on any federally funded project

Ethnicity Definition:

Hispanic or Latino. A person of Mexican, Puerto Rican, Cuban, South or Central American, or other Spanish culture or origin, regardless of race.

Race Definitions:

American Indian or Alaska Native. A person having origins in any of the original peoples of North and South America (including Central America), and who maintains tribal affiliation or community attachment.

Asian. A person having origins in any of the original peoples of the Far East, Southeast Asia, or the Indian subcontinent including, for example, Cambodia, China, India, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Pakistan, the Philippine Islands, Thailand, and Vietnam.

Black or African American. A person having origins in any of the black racial groups of Africa.

Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander. A person having origins in any of the original peoples of Hawaii, Guam, Samoa, or other Pacific Islands.

White. A person having origins in any of the original peoples of Europe, the Middle East, or North Africa.

WHY THIS INFORMATION IS BEING REQUESTED:

The Federal Government has a continuing commitment to monitor the operation of its review and award processes to identify and address any inequities based on gender, race, ethnicity, or disability of its proposed PIs/PDs. To gather information needed for this important task, the proposer should submit a single copy of this form for each identified PI/PD with each proposal. Submission of the requested information is voluntary and will not affect the organization's eligibility for an award. However, information not submitted will seriously undermine the statistical validity, and therefore the usefulness, of information received from others. Any individual not wishing to submit some or all the information should check the box provided for this purpose. (The exceptions are the PI/PD name and the information about prior Federal support, the last question above.)

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DEVIATION AUTHORIZATION (if Applicable)

DEVIATION AUTHORIZATION:

23 June 2000

Mr. Simon N. Stephenson
Arctic Research Support and Logistics Manager
Office of Polar Programs
National Science Foundation
Arlington, VA 22230
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COVER SHEET FOR PROPOSAL TO THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION

PROGRAM ANNOUNCEMENT/SOLICITATION NO./CLOSING DATE/if not in response to a program announcement/solicitation enter NSF 01-2					FOR NSF USE ONLY	
NSF 00-2					NSF PROPOSAL NUMBER	
FOR CONSIDERATION BY NSF ORGANIZATION UNIT(S) (Indicate the most specific unit known, i.e. program, division, etc.)						
OPP - ARCTIC RESRCH SUPPRT & LOGISTI						
DATE RECEIVED	NUMBER OF COPIES	DIVISION ASSIGNED	FUND CODE	DUNS# (Data Universal Numbering System)	FILE LOCATION	
EMPLOYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (EIN) OR TAXPAYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (TIN)		SHOW PREVIOUS AWARD NO. IF THIS IS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> A RENEWAL <input type="checkbox"/> AN ACCOMPLISHMENT-BASED RENEWAL		IS THIS PROPOSAL BEING SUBMITTED TO ANOTHER FEDERAL AGENCY? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IF YES, LIST ACRONYMS(S)		
920137088		9727899				
NAME OF ORGANIZATION TO WHICH AWARD SHOULD BE MADE			ADDRESS OF AWARDEE ORGANIZATION, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			
AWARDEE ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)			600 University Avenue, Suite 1			
5300001191			Fairbanks, AK. 99709			
NAME OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT FROM ABOVE			ADDRESS OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
PERFORMING ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)						
IS AWARDEE ORGANIZATION (Check All That Apply) (See GPG II.C For Definitions) <input type="checkbox"/> FOR-PROFIT ORGANIZATION <input type="checkbox"/> SMALL BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> MINORITY BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> WOMAN-OWNED BUSINESS						
TITLE OF PROPOSED PROJECT Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program						
REQUESTED AMOUNT \$ 6,519,341		PROPOSED DURATION (1-60 MONTHS) 60 months		REQUESTED STARTING DATE 01/01/01		SHOW RELATED PREPROPOSAL NO., IF APPLICABLE
CHECK APPROPRIATE BOX(ES) IF THIS PROPOSAL INCLUDES ANY OF THE ITEMS LISTED BELOW						
<input type="checkbox"/> BEGINNING INVESTIGATOR (GPG I.A)			<input type="checkbox"/> VERTEBRATE ANIMALS (GPG II.C.11) IACUC App. Date _____			
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<input type="checkbox"/> PROPRIETARY & PRIVILEGED INFORMATION (GPG I.B, II.C.6)			Exemption Subsection _____ or IRB App. Date _____			
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<input type="checkbox"/> HISTORIC PLACES (GPG II.C.9)			<input type="checkbox"/> HIGH RESOLUTION GRAPHICS/OTHER GRAPHICS WHERE EXACT COLOR REPRESENTATION IS REQUIRED FOR PROPER INTERPRETATION (GPG I.E.1)			
<input type="checkbox"/> SMALL GRANT FOR EXPLOR. RESEARCH (SGER) (GPG II.C.11)						
PI/PD DEPARTMENT ARCUS			PI/PD POSTAL ADDRESS 600 University Avenue, Suite 1			
PI/PD FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604			Fairbanks, AK 99709 United States			
NAMES (TYPED)		High Degree	Yr of Degree	Telephone Number	Electronic Mail Address	
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CO-PI/PD						
CO-PI/PD						
CO-PI/PD						
CO-PI/PD						

CERTIFICATION PAGE

Certification for Principal Investigators and Co-Principal Investigators:

I certify to the best of my knowledge that:

- (1) the statements herein (excluding scientific hypotheses and scientific opinions) are true and complete, and
- (2) the text and graphics herein as well as any accompanying publications or other documents, unless otherwise indicated, are the original work of the signatories or individuals working under their supervision. I agree to accept responsibility for the scientific conduct of the project and to provide the required progress reports if an award is made as a result of this proposal.

I understand that the willful provision of false information or concealing a material fact in this proposal or any other communication submitted to NSF is a criminal offense (U.S.Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

Name (Typed)	Signature	Social Security No.*	Date
PI/PD Wendy K Warnick		*ON FASTLANE SUBMISSIONS* SSNs are confidential and are not displayed	
Co-PI/PD			

Certification for Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant:

By signing and submitting this proposal, the individual applicant or the authorized official of the applicant institution is: (1) certifying that statements made herein are true and complete to the best of his/her knowledge; and (2) agreeing to accept the obligation to comply with NSF award terms and conditions if an award is made as a result of this application. Further, the applicant is hereby providing certifications regarding debarment and suspension, drug-free workplace, and lobbying activities (see below), as set forth in Grant Proposal Guide (GPG), NSF 01-2. Willful provision of false information in this application and its supporting documents or in reports required under an ensuring award is a criminal offense (U. S. Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

In addition, if the applicant institution employs more than fifty persons, the authorized official of the applicant institution is certifying that the institution has implemented a written and enforced conflict of interest policy that is consistent with the provisions of Grant Policy Manual Section 510; that to the best of his/her knowledge, all financial disclosures required by that conflict of interest policy have been made; and that all identified conflicts of interest will have been satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated prior to the institution's expenditure of any funds under the award, in accordance with the institution's conflict of interest policy. Conflict which cannot be satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated must be disclosed to NSF.

Debarment Certification

(If answer "yes", please provide explanation.)

Is the organization or its principals presently debarred, suspended, proposed for debarment, declared ineligible, or voluntarily excluded from covered transactions by any Federal department or agency?

Yes

No

Certification Regarding Lobbying

This certification is required for an award of a Federal contract, grant, or cooperative agreement exceeding \$100,000 and for an award of a Federal loan or a commitment providing for the United States to insure or guarantee a loan exceeding \$150,000.

Certification for Contracts, Grants, Loans and Cooperative Agreements

The undersigned certifies, to the best of his or her knowledge and belief, that:

- (1) No federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid, by or on behalf of the undersigned, to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with the awarding of any federal contract, the making of any Federal grant, the making of any Federal loan, the entering into of any cooperative agreement, and the extension, continuation, renewal, amendment, or modification of any Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement.
- (2) If any funds other than Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with this Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement, the undersigned shall complete and submit Standard Form-LLL, "Disclosure Form to Report Lobbying," in accordance with its instructions.
- (3) The undersigned shall require that the language of this certification be included in the award documents for all subawards at all tiers including subcontracts, subgrants, and contracts under grants, loans, and cooperative agreements and that all subrecipients shall certify and disclose accordingly.

This certification is a material representation of fact upon which reliance was placed when this transaction was made or entered into. Submission of this certification is a prerequisite for making or entering into this transaction imposed by section 1352, title 31, U.S. Code. Any person who fails to file the required certification shall be subject to a civil penalty of not less than \$10,000 and not more than \$100,000 for each such failure.

AUTHORIZED ORGANIZATIONAL REPRESENTATIVE	SIGNATURE	DATE
NAME/TITLE (TYPED) Wendy K. Warnick		08/23/00
TELEPHONE NUMBER 907-474-1600	ELECTRONIC MAIL ADDRESS warnick@arcus.org	FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604

*SUBMISSION OF SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBERS IS VOLUNTARY AND WILL NOT AFFECT THE ORGANIZATION'S ELIGIBILITY FOR AN AWARD. HOWEVER, THEY ARE AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE INFORMATION SYSTEM AND ASSIST IN PROCESSING THE PROPOSAL. SSN SOLICITED UNDER NSF ACT OF 1950, AS AMENDED.

PROJECT SUMMARY: ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT TO THE U.S. ARCTIC SCIENCE PROGRAM, 2001–2005

The Arctic Research Consortium of the United States (ARCUS) proposes to the National Science Foundation's (NSF) Office of Polar Programs (OPP) a cooperative agreement over the next five years to provide organizational support to the NSF OPP Arctic Sciences Section to develop, promote, and implement arctic research and education. Building on its major accomplishments—outlined in the Prior Support section—ARCUS will continue to serve the goals of the NSF Arctic programs by nurturing the orderly growth of arctic research through tasks that cannot be accomplished as effectively by individual researchers, institutions, agencies, or by currently existing advisory bodies.

Based on an excellent track record of prior work, and in cooperation with the NSF Arctic Sciences Section and the arctic science community, ARCUS proposes to carry out 24 tasks to provide organizational support to the U.S. Arctic science programs. The proposed work falls into four main categories:

- Arctic science planning—coordinating science planning for the arctic research community at several levels, including continuing examination of logistical requirements with the goal of improved access for all researchers in the Arctic;
- Organizational support for research programs included in the Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section—the Arctic System Science Program (ARCSS), the Arctic Social Sciences Program (ASSP), and the Arctic Natural Sciences Program (ANS);
- Development and coordination of arctic science educational activities; and
- Information and outreach activities to disseminate information about arctic research to the scientific community, policy and decision-makers, and to the public.

The proposed tasks in these four categories will enhance current and future arctic science objectives. Through these activities ARCUS will:

- increase communication among arctic researchers, academic institutions, federal and Alaska state agencies, and logistical/field facilities and projects;
- inform policy-makers, educators, and funding sources—including federal agencies, private foundations, corporate bodies—on the needs, opportunities, and benefits in arctic research; and
- improve offerings and programs in arctic science education.

ARCUS' work will improve U.S. arctic research and education efforts by increasing the participation of all interested arctic groups and individuals, fostering interdisciplinary exchanges, and making effective use of available resources. The global significance and worldwide interest generated by

Scene in Ny Ålesund, Svalbard, Norway (photo by Olvind Toien).

arctic research results put them literally "all over the map." To sustain these diverse interests in support of arctic research, a broad and inclusive mechanism for commu-

nication and coordination such as ARCUS is needed. ARCUS proposes to continue serving the NSF and the research community by coordinating planning, disseminating information, and creating a focal point for education and new opportunities in arctic sciences.

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Section	Total No. of Pages in Section	Page No.* (Optional)*
Cover Sheet (NSF Form 1207) (Submit Page 2 with original proposal only)		
A Project Summary (not to exceed 1 page)	1	_____
B Table of Contents (NSF Form 1359)	1	_____
C Project Description (plus Results from Prior NSF Support) (not to exceed 15 pages) (Exceed only if allowed by a specific program announcement/solicitation or if approved in advance by the appropriate NSF Assistant Director or designee)	24	_____
D References Cited	2	_____
E Biographical Sketches (Not to exceed 2 pages each)	2	_____
F Budget (NSF Form 1030, plus up to 3 pages of budget justification)	11	_____
G Current and Pending Support (NSF Form 1239)	1	_____
H Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources (NSF Form 1363)	1	_____
I Special Information/Supplementary Documentation	0	_____
J Appendix (List below.) (Include only if allowed by a specific program announcement/ solicitation or if approved in advance by the appropriate NSF Assistant Director or designee)	_____	_____
Appendix Items:		

*Proposers may select any numbering mechanism for the proposal. The entire proposal however, must be paginated. Complete both columns only if the proposal is numbered consecutively.

PROPOSAL TO PROVIDE ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT TO THE U.S. ARCTIC SCIENCE PROGRAM, 2001–2005

The local and global significance of arctic research is growing rapidly. Accumulating evidence shows that the Arctic and its residents are particularly vulnerable to environmental, social, and economic changes. Research results show that arctic climate and ecosystems are changing substantially (Oechel *et al.* 2000, Serreze *et al.* 2000). Climate models suggest both that the arctic environment will react particularly sensitively to global climate change and that changes in the Arctic will have major effects on the global climate system (Manabe and Stouffer 1994). The observed changes, and the processes that cause them, appear to be linked to the whole Northern Hemisphere, involving physical characteristics in the atmosphere, ocean, and on land (Belkin *et al.* 1998). Early results suggest that these physical changes are affecting the arctic biosphere, and many arctic residents report ecosystem changes (Gibson and Schullinger 1998). Rapid social changes also are taking place in the Arctic, especially in political and economic systems. From relative self-sufficiency in the recent past, arctic peoples now are incorporated into national states and the global economy. In some places, arctic peoples are gaining political and economic power while in others, they face massive social, political, and economic changes (Fondahl 1999, Korsmo 1997).

To address these and other interrelated phenomena, research in the Arctic increasingly takes an integrated, interdisciplinary approach (IARPC 1991). This broadened approach, driven largely by researchers seeking to understand the full context of their studies as well as the wider implications of their results, poses major challenges to existing academic and funding structures that developed largely to support single investigators working within one academic discipline (Metzger and Zare 1999). Planning and carrying out interdisciplinary research

thus requires a dedicated effort to design research programs, including mechanisms for competition and selection, and to integrate and synthesize the results of many investigators across disciplines. For such an effort to succeed in the dispersed arctic research community, its members need to participate in and be informed about the relevant planning, integrating, and synthesizing activities. The Arctic Research Policy Act of 1984 recognized this need, designating the National Science Foundation as the lead federal agency for arctic research.

In addition to disciplinary integration and collaboration, research in the Arctic involves geographic diversity as researchers examine a huge range of phenomena, from physical processes to ecological dynamics to institutional politics, at local and regional scales and compare results from locations around the Arctic. Scientific projects increasingly encompass the circumpolar region as a whole, requiring year-round access to the Arctic and stimulating international collaborations (IASC 2000). Funded by several different federal and international agencies, researchers investigate arctic phenomena on land, sea, ice, and air, working in international waters as well as in all the countries of the circumpolar north (USARC 1999, IARPC 1987-2000).

By creating geographic, cultural, and disciplinary links to meet these and other challenges of research today, the Arctic

Research Consortium of the United States (ARCUS) serves the diverse and disseminated arctic research community and provides the means for arctic researchers to translate broad scientific goals into specific and detailed implementation plans and to integrate their research efforts effectively and efficiently. In particular, ARCUS provides essential organizational support for the development of efficiently managed arctic research programs by:

- facilitating the identification of interdisciplinary research priorities,
- bringing these research opportunities to the attention of relevant funding sources,
- advocating for arctic research support in appropriate policy circles, and
- providing information and assistance for the dissemination of research results and integration across programs.

ABOUT ARCUS

ARCUS is a non-profit membership corporation, currently consisting of 41 institutions that are organized and operated for educational, professional, and scientific purposes.

Based in the scientific community, ARCUS represents a broad range of disciplines that are widely dispersed geographically. By supporting, enhancing, and extending the capabilities of the arctic research community, ARCUS fosters the transfer of knowledge, nationally and internationally.

Among the organizations involved in arctic research and engineering, the role of ARCUS is unique. Working with the arctic research community and the agencies that support research in the Arctic, ARCUS facilitates and participates in the entire process

of planning, execution, and management of integrated arctic research programs—including devising early strategies, advocating programs to researchers and funding agencies, establishing the programs, and disseminating their findings. ARCUS bridges the development of broad arctic research priorities and strategies (tasks for the Polar Research Board), the development of national arctic research policies (U.S. Arctic Research Commission), the promotion of international collaboration (International Arctic Science Committee and others), and coordination of the funding agencies (Inter-agency Arctic Research Policy Committee).

Educational and research institutions established the consortium in 1998, with the support and encouragement of several federal agencies, including the National Science Foundation, to strengthen and advance arctic research to meet national needs by working toward the following objectives:

- producing improvements in United States arctic research,
- building a cohesive arctic research community of scientists and scholars,
- opening avenues for interdisciplinary approaches, the introduction of new techniques, and the widening of scientific participation, and
- sharing new information with the broader scientific community and the public.

With the sponsorship of relevant agencies, ARCUS provides community leadership by convening science planning committees and working groups and by sponsoring meetings to address various science, policy, and advocacy concerns. ARCUS emphasizes the importance of distributing research results to the scientific community, arctic communities, and the public. ARCUS draws on and works with the academic community and with the appropriate program managers in funding agencies to develop and focus program recommendations and to suggest appropriate implementation strategies.

ARCUS is a key communication link among investigators, institutions, providers of information and logistical support, and funding agencies through databases, an extensive web site with links to member organizations and research projects, other electronic media, a newsletter, community contacts, and member representatives. ARCUS seeks to assist the implementation of arctic research in the most productive—and efficient—manner possible. ARCUS serves the goals of the arctic programs by taking on those tasks needed for the orderly growth of arctic research that cannot be accomplished in isolation by individual researchers, institutions, agencies, or other advisory bodies.

ARCUS has demonstrated that an organization with roots in the academic sector can effectively assist the federal agencies that support or conduct arctic research by promoting and managing these research opportunities and their challenges. ARCUS has an excellent track record in coordinating interdisciplinary science planning and in mobilizing the academic community to promote and organize important research and education efforts. ARCUS has brought arctic researchers together to discuss shared issues, resulting in a greater understanding of the Arctic and its impact on the broader global issues. The impact of these collaborations has reached far beyond the circumpolar North.

ARCUS MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE

The ARCUS organizational structure supports planning and implementation of initiatives on behalf of the arctic research community and at the request of the National Science Foundation and other government agencies and develops programs that

benefit the general accumulation of knowledge, research institutions, individual researchers, and arctic communities.

A 13-member Board of Directors, nominated by the arctic research and education community, governs ARCUS. The Council of ARCUS, consisting of an authorized representative from each member institution, elects the Board of Directors except for the President, who is elected by the board itself. The Council meets annually to conduct corporate business and to host the *Arctic Forum* (see page C-8). The Board of Directors and Council further the mission of ARCUS by broadening the participation and support of the arctic research community in ARCUS activities.

The Executive Director, Wendy Warnick, manages the programs and activities of ARCUS—helping arctic researchers develop and implement science plans and education programs, orchestrating advocacy and information efforts, and coordinating scientific workshops. Wendy has served ARCUS for over eight years and has an excellent understanding of the scientific, monetary, and logistical issues facing arctic researchers. She has worked closely with over 45 boards, working groups, and advisory committees; countless individual researchers; and dozens of agency personnel. She directs a staff which is especially skilled in synthesizing and integrating scientific information from many sources and presenting it both accurately and comprehensibly to diverse audiences. Although few in number, the ARCUS staff is a closely knit team of exceptionally skilled and technologically savvy professionals. The staff has organized over 40 meetings and workshops, arranged travel and processed expense reports for 830 participants, and published over 1,520 pages of concise, coherent, and synthesized proceedings and recommendations. ARCUS has an established record of sound fiscal and administrative systems; the Business Manager is a Certified Public Accountant with 14 years experience.

RESULTS FROM PRIOR NSF SUPPORT

ARCUS has received support from NSF for the past eight years under the following awards titled Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program:

- OPP-9727899 – January 1998 through December 2000 - \$2,889,083
- OPP-9404321 – May 1994 through April 1998 - \$1,655,495
- DPP-9210133 – October 1992 through December 1993 - \$544,305.

The nature of the work proposed for a new five-year cooperative agreement follows directly from the results of prior work described in this section. The importance and significance of the ongoing tasks are discussed in more detail in the Project Description section of this proposal. The results of prior work from previous NSF funding are described in four major categories:

- Arctic science planning;
- Organizational support for research programs included in the Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section;
- Development and coordination of arctic science educational activities; and
- Information and outreach activities to disseminate arctic research information.

ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

Scientific Planning

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research for over eight years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents. These documents reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. Accomplishments include:

- ARCUS facilitated, with NSF, the selection of an 18-member U.S. scientific delegation to participate in an August 1999 workshop hosted by Norwegian research organizations and held in Svalbard, Norway.

ARCUS convened the workshop in conjunction with the Norwegian hosts and published *Opportunities for Collaboration between the United States and Norway in Arctic Research* in September 2000.

The recommendations are expected to form the basis of future collaborations between the two

countries that will result in development of new facilities, improvements to existing ones, and sharing of previously restricted resources.

- A seven-member working group, appointed by ARCUS, solicited broad community participation in the development of a scientific strategic plan for arctic marine research. The resulting recommendations were published in February 1999 in *Marine Science in the Arctic: A Strategy*.
- Twenty-eight scientists representing a wide spectrum of arctic research interests identified critical research questions and support requirements during a community workshop held in September 1998. The discussion and subsequent recommendations are described in *Opportunities in Arctic Research: Final Report*, a white paper submitted to NSF in December 1998. This report served as the basis for the Long-term Observatory Announcement of Opportunity.

Arctic Research Support and Logistics

ARCUS has been active in community advocacy for improved arctic research logistics since 1989.

- In 1992, ARCUS initiated community planning for upgrading facilities at Toolik Field Station in Alaska. The resulting report, *Toolik Field Station: The Second 20 Years*, was published by ARCUS in 1996. Significant improvements to the field station's facilities have been implemented in the past four years as a consequence of this planning process.
- *Logistics Recommendations for an Improved U.S. Arctic Research Capability*, published by ARCUS in 1997, documented the importance of a strong U.S. arctic logistics capability and recommended improvements to arctic logistics. An ARCUS-led committee, working over a period of several years, canvassed arctic researchers, consulted existing evaluations of logistical needs, and sought wide consultation with the arctic research community to develop these recommendations. Following publication of the 1997 report, Congress appropriated \$22 million in FY 99 and \$25 million in FY 00 for arctic research support and logistics.
- In 1999, ARCUS published *The Future of an Arctic Resource: Recommendations from the Barrow Area Research Support Workshop*, based on a 1998 workshop and subsequent arctic research community contributions. This report noted that responding to the outstanding research opportunities in the region of Barrow, Alaska was hampered by the limited support available and recommended appropriate improvements to research infrastructure and support. As a result, NSF has initiated expansion of the logistical capability in the Barrow area, including increased funding for logistics support and planning for improved facilities.
- ARCUS has been developing additional features and increased utility for the Arctic

Logistics Information and Support (ALIAS) web site. ARCUS surveyed the arctic research community about logistics resources, user needs and priorities, and useful information networks and is using that information to develop an interactive and searchable Internet resource serving as a clearinghouse and portal for arctic logistics and research support information.

ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

Arctic System Science Program

ARCUS coordinates science planning and other activities for the NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program through the ARCSS Committee (AC). The Committee serves as the focal point for integration among the many ARCSS components and projects and ensures that the research activities are in keeping with the overall goals and objectives of the ARCSS Program.

- In May 2000, ARCUS published *Understanding Global Change in the Arctic*, a

full-color six-page brochure outlining the accomplishments and future objectives of the ARCSS Program for a broad general audience. The brochure provides the arctic research community with an informative and useful aid in outreach and education efforts.

- ARCUS published the second ARCSS science plan, *Toward Prediction of the Arctic System*, in 1998. AC meetings held in 1999 and 2000 continued to advance the implementation of recommendations for integrative research on the arctic system and global environmental change through integrated assessment of climate change,

arctic hydrologic cycles and feedbacks, and integration of contemporary and paleoenvironmental terrestrial data. The first ARCSS science plan, *Arctic System Science: A Plan for Integration*, was published by ARCUS in 1993.

Earlier ARCSS program work includes:

- An October 1995 workshop resulted in implementation of the Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) initiative as described in *People and the Arctic: A Prospectus for Research on the Human Dimensions of the Arctic System*, published by ARCUS in 1997.
- At a May 1996 All-Investigator Workshop, a gathering of ARCSS investigators, researchers from other major programs, and agency representatives presented key findings and developed recommendations about scientific priorities in ARCSS research. Abstracts and recommendations were published in *Toward an Arctic System Synthesis: Results and Recommendations*.
- A January 1996 workshop and subsequent report, *Modeling the Arctic System: The State of Modeling in the ARCSS Program*, provided the NSF with guidelines and priorities for modeling-related issues including phasing and development of ARCSS modeling efforts.
- A special session at the 1996 AAAS Arctic Division conference titled *Partnership Building and Ways of Knowing: A Dialogue*. The session brought together scientists and arctic residents to share views on the role of science in arctic communities and the role of traditional knowledge in western science.

Arctic Social Sciences Program

ARCUS coordinated community science planning to assess the status of arctic social sciences research, to stimulate creative thinking and interaction about a variety of research areas, and to expand and augment the work done so far under the Arctic Social Sciences Program.

- A statement of opportunities for the NSF Office of Polar Programs Arctic Social Sciences Program was published in July 1999. The report, *Arctic Social Sciences: Opportunities in Arctic Research*, was the product of a workshop held in October 1997 and subsequent community discussions. The Arctic Social Sciences Program has since experienced an increase in the number and quality of proposals received.

ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

Arctic Science Education Activities

ARCUS has long provided leadership and direction within the arctic community to improve the quality of science research and to increase people's understanding of and appreciation for science and the Arctic.

An Arctic Science Education Working Group (ASEWG), convened by ARCUS in March 2000, developed recommendations to the NSF for the implementation of research-centered arctic science education programs that will engage teachers, students, and arctic residents in scientific research; build effective partnerships among academic, agency, arctic community, and education participants; and increase public awareness of arctic research and the importance of the arctic region. Recommendations from the working group will be published in December 2000 and will assist the formulation of future education initiatives for the Arctic Section of the Office of Polar Programs at NSF.

At a 1997 ARCUS-hosted workshop, scientists, educators, and others recommended the systematic introduction of arctic science into K-12 classrooms, using emerg-

ing technologies, contributions from indigenous peoples, and collaborations between researchers and educators. The 1997 workshop also recommended outreach activities to increase awareness of arctic research. ARCUS has initiated several efforts implementing these recommendations:

- Developing integrated curriculum materials that incorporate both knowledge of indigenous peoples and National Science Education Standards (which apply to kindergarten through 12th-grade students) in collaboration with the Alaska Federation of Natives and the University of Alaska Fairbanks through the NSF-funded Rural Systemic Initiative and other education organizations.
- Providing coordination and program assistance to the NSF Teachers Experiencing Antarctica and the Arctic (TEA) program in 1998 and 1999. Four teachers traveled to the Arctic in 1998 and three teachers in 1999. Arctic TEA participants use their hands-on research experience to convey to their students, colleagues, and communities the relevance of science to our daily lives in innovative ways that emphasize active participation in the scientific process.
- Assisting U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, the North Slope Borough Department of Wildlife Management, and several Alaska school districts with teacher and student placements in a joint outreach and education program designed to involve local community members in monitoring of endangered species living in the Arctic. Several students involved in the project have become interested in careers in wildlife management and have participated in scientific and educational follow-up activities.

Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS initiated the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series in 2000 to foster interdisciplinary and international scientific exchange as well as science education on the local

level. The Series provides travel support for organizations wishing to host a visiting scientist or arctic expert. Applications have been approved in the first year for six U.S. experts to speak domestically and abroad and for three foreign speakers to visit the U.S. for a series of presentations.

Applications and community feedback received indicate that this program fills an important and previously unmet need. The Arctic Visiting Speakers Series is not limited to academic speakers and institutions. Speakers and organizations from arctic communities are strongly encouraged to participate. Academic host institutions are urged to maximize the impact of a speaker's visit by submitting joint applications in partnership with community organizations such as schools and libraries.

INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

Witness the Arctic Newsletter

Witness the Arctic has been published biannually since 1993 and provides information on current arctic research efforts and findings, significant research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic research, international activities, and profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts. *Witness* currently serves an audience of over 6,500 arctic scientists, educators, agency personnel, and policy makers and is available both on-line and in print.

Arctic Info Listserver

Arctic Info is an e-mail listserv serving the arctic research community and maintained by ARCUS. The listserv provides timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position

announcements, and other useful news. Anyone can submit information but all postings are reviewed and verified before distribution. Over 3,100 researchers currently subscribe to Arctic Info. More than 530 announcements have been posted since the listserver was initiated in 1996.

Web Site (<http://www.arcus.org>)

ARCUS maintains a web site with information important to the research community, links to many arctic research sites and activities, links to important arctic publications, a searchable archive of Arctic Info listserver postings, a calendar of arctic-relevant events, and a searchable directory of arctic researchers. All ARCUS publications are available on-line at the web site.

Directory of Arctic Researchers

The *Directory of Arctic Researchers* was initiated in 1994 to facilitate networking and collaboration in arctic research and education efforts between individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders. The contents of the directory, which includes U.S. and international arctic researchers, are developed through surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions. The directory now contains over 2,800 researchers and is available as a searchable database at the ARCUS web site with simple and complex search capabilities by scientific specialty and basic contact information. The directory and disciplinary cross-reference are available on the web site as PDF files.

Arctic Data and Information Resources

ARCUS convened the Arctic Data and Information Resources Working Group

(DIRWOG) in 1992. DIRWOG completed and published *Arctic Information and Data: A Guide to Selected Resources*, presenting brief descriptions of information resources pertaining to the Arctic. A second edition was published by ARCUS in 1996. An on-line version of the *Guide* was prepared in 1997 and is searchable on the ARCUS web site.

Arctic Community Outreach

The annual *Arctic Forum*, convened by ARCUS and held each year since 1994 in conjunction with ARCUS' annual meeting, brings together investigators, federal agency officials, and students for presentations on new and cutting-edge arctic research. The interdisciplinary nature of the program has resulted in important contacts and collaborations among researchers, agencies, and countries that do not typically occur at

discipline-focused gatherings. The proceedings of the *Arctic Forum* have been published annually since 1998.

ARCUS' ability to bring individuals and groups together for collaboration and information sharing is a valuable contribution to the arctic research community.

Through extensive experience and interactions over the past ten years, we have developed a broad knowledge of the arctic research community that transcends disciplinary, geographical, and governmental boundaries. It is not possible to enumerate within the constraints of this proposal the many fruitful connections made among individuals and institutions through ARCUS activities. More information about ARCUS activities and accomplishments is available on our web site (<http://www.arcus.org>) and in many of the publications referenced in Section D.

PROPOSED COOPERATIVE AGREEMENT ACTIVITIES, 2001 TO 2005

Based on the above record, and in cooperation with the NSF Arctic Sciences Section and the scientific community, ARCUS proposes to carry out 4 tasks to provide organizational support to the NSF arctic science programs. These tasks fall into the same categories in which we described the results of prior support.

- Arctic science planning—coordinating science planning for the arctic research community at several levels, including continuing examination of logistical requirements with the goal of improved access for all researchers in the Arctic;
- Organizational support for research programs included in the Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section—the Arctic System Science Program, the Arctic Social Sciences Program, and the Arctic Natural Sciences Program;
- Development and coordination of arctic science educational activities; and
- Information and outreach activities disseminating timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, and to the public.

An additional 5th “task” is the provision of core support for ARCUS’ NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the infrastructure necessary to support this work regardless of the specific nature of activities from year-to-year.

Much of the planning and organizing work conducted by ARCUS on behalf of the arctic research community consists of several related activities, which are described here to outline the methods that ARCUS uses to achieve broad and consistent representation of the arctic research community.

- Workshop and meeting coordination: ARCUS works with the relevant scientific community to determine the scope and focus of the workshop or planning meeting, including goals and objectives, impor-

tant scientific topics, key participants, and the appropriate extent of community participation. Frequently, a small organizing committee is appointed, and ARCUS works with the committee to develop the meeting agenda or program, invite speakers and participants, and plan the meeting logistics, including the venue, participant travel and lodging, and appropriate meeting support. Meeting coordination typically includes organizing details ranging from coffee and refreshment arrangements, and preparing and distributing the meeting program and background material, to providing highly technical computer, network/Internet connectivity, and audiovisual support. ARCUS provides travel support for many participants, including making travel and lodging arrangements. ARCUS provides information about the upcoming event to the relevant groups, or broadly, via the web site, listserver, and other dissemination mechanisms.

- Publication development: Many planning efforts organized by ARCUS have resulted in a publication summarizing the arctic research community's perspectives on a particular issue. ARCUS works with the workshop participants and scientific community to prepare draft content, which requires a clear understanding of the goals and context of the planning process, key scientific concepts, and the needs and priorities of the particular research community. Contributions must then be integrated, synthesized, and edited to present a coherent and compelling summary of the planning effort, and figures, graphics and the basic report layout must be prepared in keeping with the contents of the report. All ARCUS reports are subjected to at least one round of review by the research community. In collaboration with the major contributors, ARCUS coordinates revisions of the draft report in

response to review comments. We believe strongly that the iterative review process and close collaboration with the research community results in substantive reports that reflect the views of this very diverse scientific community. ARCUS handles the publication process, including printing requirements, press checks, and distribution of the finished reports. During the past eight years, preparation of these well-integrated, carefully reviewed publications has required an average of 13.3 months from the time of a community workshop or inception of the planning process to the distribution of the report, with a range of one to 24 months. Analysis of a comparable number of scientific planning reports, prepared and published by other entities during the same period, and selected for their similarity to ARCUS publications, showed an average publication time of 14.8 months with a range of four to 39 months.

- Information and outreach activities: ARCUS responds to community needs by delivering a wide range of information in an efficient, timely manner. Several structured outreach activities, including the newsletter, the Arctic Info listserver, the *Directory of Arctic Researchers*, and the ARCUS web site, were initially developed in response to requests for assistance or information from members of the scientific community. In addition to these structured activities, and because of our broad network of connections with the individuals and institutions that make up the arctic research community, ARCUS is often called on informally to provide information about arctic research efforts and resources. We frequently receive thanks from researchers, educators, and administrators for exposing them to relevant and important findings and issues that they would not have received through their normal institutional or disciplinary channels.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

Logistics Planning

TASK 1.1: ARCTIC RESEARCH SUPPORT AND LOGISTICS

ARCUS formed the Arctic Research Support and Logistics Working Group (RSLWG) in 1999. Supported by the NSF-OPP, the working group was tasked to carry on and expand upon the work of the ad hoc Logistics Working Group (LWG), formed by ARCUS in 1995 and sponsored by the U.S. Arctic Research Commission and NSF. The product of the first ad hoc planning process was the 1997 publication of the report *Logistics Recommendations for an Improved U.S. Arctic Research Capability*, which has provided effective guidance on logistics improvements to the U.S. Arctic Research Commission and to the NSF-OPP Arctic Program (see Results from Prior Support).

Since 1997, the arctic logistics budget of NSF-OPP has increased substantially and the U.S. arctic logistics infrastructure has improved, while recent findings raise new questions and may shift the priorities of arctic research. In this dynamic situation, it is essential that arctic researchers continue to work together to guide science-driven planning and implementation of research support and logistics for U.S. arctic research programs.

Through the activities of the RSLWG, ARCUS will support the research community in providing long-term expertise and advice on arctic logistics and science support issues

for the NSF-OPP. ARCUS and the RSLWG will promote and assist the development of an appropriately strengthened U.S. arctic logistics capability through the following specific activities over the next five years:

- Gathering community input: In 2000, ARCUS, with the RSLWG, initiated an online and email community survey and held the first of several planned community town meetings (during the *Arctic Forum*, sponsored by ARCUS in May 2000 in Washington D.C.). Based on initial discussions, the RSLWG is developing draft recommendations to elicit further advice from the research community.
- Preparing the next edition of *Logistics Recommendations for an Improved U.S. Arctic Research Capability*: The 1997 report was designed to be a "living" document that would be periodically updated to reflect changing science priorities. The new report, based on the information gathered from the research community as outlined above, will be published in fall of 2001, with the next major update planned for December 2005.
- Preparing a five-year implementation plan: In an associated task, the working group will provide information to the NSF-OPP Program Manager for Arctic Research Support and Logistics by developing a five-year implementation plan of research support and logistics for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section. The Program Manager will contribute to the development of this plan by compiling and communicating to the working group implementation requirements based on logistics needs identified in proposals received, discussions with other NSF program managers, discussions with other arctic logistics experts, and from attending workshops and meetings. The implementation plan will be developed concurrently with the updated logistics report and will reflect those research support priorities identified in the report. The implementation plan will be published in spring of 2002.

- Guiding the development of the ALIAS web site: The working group will guide the ongoing creation and maintenance of the Arctic Logistics Information and Support (ALIAS) web site now under development by ARCUS (see activity 1.2).

The structure and process of the Research Support and Logistics Working Group provides an in-place community-focused planning mechanism to help the NSF-OPP and other agencies respond flexibly to emerging scientific issues and evolving research support and logistics priorities and impediments over the next five years. The ongoing RSLWG activities will facilitate community discussions, recognition of new priorities and needs, identification of new scientific questions and opportunities, and appropriate recommendations for development and implementation of logistics support. These activities will include an annual town meeting at the interdisciplinary *Arctic Forum*, meetings of opportunity associated with arctic conferences and disciplinary meetings, periodic publication of recommendations, and the use of Internet resources for ongoing surveys and situational communications to support community involvement in academic and agency-based planning for research support and logistics.

TASK 1.2: LOGISTICS INTERNET RESOURCES; ARCTIC LOGISTICS INFORMATION AND SUPPORT (ALIAS)

The Arctic Logistics Information and Support (ALIAS) project consists of the design, creation, and maintenance of a web site to serve as the online portal to the arctic logistics and research support available in all eight arctic nations. As the primary access point, the ALIAS portal will enable researchers to acquire information on all aspects of arctic research support and logistics (*i.e.*, potential field sites, options for air transportation, local permitting requirements, communications support). Information available via the ALIAS site will be used by researchers to prepare proposals and plan the conduct of their research. ALIAS also will help

researchers to assess the feasibility of working in a specific area, to see what research is currently being conducted in a given area and by whom, to review maps and publications from research conducted in the area, and to make useful scientific and logistics support contacts.

Development goals include a phased process of building an initial simple user interface providing basic logistics resource information, which will be on-line in December 2000, followed by creation of a data-base-backed interactive site for contributions of up-to-date information on research sites, logistics providers, discussions of logistics needs and problems, and to identify changeable resources, including human resources and community contacts. Information from existing web sites and databases will be identified with an annotated link or may be hosted seamlessly within the ALIAS site. Information not available elsewhere will be collected, databased, and hosted directly by ALIAS.

The development of ALIAS and companion logistics Internet resources is the responsibility of a full-time project manager, along with a development team drawn from ARCUS staff, web site design and database experts, and two to four logistics resource consultants for specific geographic areas or types of resource. The development of ALIAS is being closely coordinated with the logistics information resources prepared by VECO Polar Resources, the current NSF arctic logistics contractor, as well as with other arctic logistics providers and experts.

Scientific Planning

TASK 1.3: PLANNING FOR INTEGRATED ARCTIC GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEMS (GIS)

ARCUS was tasked by NSF in 2000 to convene a workshop to review potential uses and requirements for integrated web-based Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to support arctic research activities. ARCUS will gather community input through the workshop and prepare recommendations to guide a development plan. The January 2001 workshop in Seattle, Washington is supported through the current cooperative agreement between NSF and ARCUS. Several follow-on activities critical to the success of this planning effort are proposed here:

- development of a white paper with preliminary recommendations to guide the direction and scope of this planning effort,
- preparation of a comprehensive report containing longer term recommendations for development and implementation, which will require considerably more community discussion and synthesis prior to publication.

In January 2001, workshop participants will assess what arctic scientific issues would benefit from an improved GIS capability and what path might be taken to develop GIS to address those issues. Participants also will consider the benefits to research, and the broader societal benefits, such as outreach and informing the public of current issues and knowledge.

Recent developments in GIS have made it much easier to run them over the Internet. GIS can be used to improve collaboration among researchers; make new links between researchers not currently collaborating, perhaps from different disciplines; and provide public access to results of past and current research, possibly to be used in educational opportunities. This draws on one of the key benefits of using GIS, which is to help users visualize data or information.

Web-based GIS has potential to be the core system in providing both simple and complex sets of information related to arctic science in geographic format. For example, a simple use could be to provide logistical information, such as where specific projects work, when they are in the field, and what resources they use. This could be presented at a variety of scales, ranging from an arctic-wide summary by discipline, to detailed maps of research plots, with the management plan of the sites and information on the history of each plot. Research sites can be linked to project web sites to provide more information. A more complex use may be to provide geographically-referenced data and analysis

An example of an international unified-arctic map depicting the distribution and properties of permafrost in the Northern Hemisphere from digital data, prepared by the International Permafrost Association (Brown et al. 1997, UNEP/GRID-Arendal 1998).

results from the research itself. This may include basic map-type data (*e.g.*, satellite imagery or digitized aerial imagery, or tables and graphs of physical parameters and analyses at a given research site).

The long-range goal of this planning process is to increase the flow of geographically-based information through the arctic research community and to the broader community. While the NSF Arctic Research Support and Logistics Program and workshop organizers expect an incremental approach to developing and implementing integrated arctic GIS in the immediate future, the planning process will include the research community's assessment of how GIS can best support arctic science in the longer term.

Questions to be addressed include:

- What key issues in arctic science could be enhanced by using GIS, particularly operating over the web; data-sharing, logistics planning, model calibration, outreach?
- What geographic data is available that is needed for many applications, *e.g.*, digital elevation models, coastline data, regional vegetation data, bathymetry, regional satellite imagery, meteorology?
- What other GIS activities related to arctic science are underway and could assist the implementation of this activity?
- How much training is needed for people using the system, and how can this be best delivered?

The workshop reports may recommend a series of activities that would lead to one or several linked pilot projects to provide tangible demonstrations or test the value of web-based GIS to arctic research. Preparation and distribution of the white paper and the subsequent, published report will be important steps in engaging the interdisciplinary scientific community and ensuring multi-agency participation in the planning and implementation of this effort. Both the white paper and the workshop report will be available for broad community review and comment prior to their submission to NSF.

TASKS 1.4-1.6: WORKSHOPS, TO BE DETERMINED

At the request of the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, this proposal includes funding for three community science planning workshops, described as "contingency workshops", in years three-five of this cooperative agreement. Over the past eight years, ARCUS has been asked on short notice nearly every year to assist with emergent science planning in the form of meetings and workshops (*e.g.*, assessing priority opportunities in arctic research in September 1998, planning for infrastructure improvements in the Barrow, Alaska region in December 1998, and assessing opportunities for collaborative U.S./Norwegian research on Svalbard in August 1999). The Arctic Section

forsees a continuing need for expeditious community science planning efforts to take advantage of new opportunities or respond to significant results, which have yet to develop fully. Responding rapidly and effectively to such requests requires organizational flexibility and sufficient in-place staff resources to address the needs in a timely manner. Planning and budgeting for such contingencies in advance will give ARCUS and the NSF Arctic Sciences Section the flexibility to respond to community science planning needs as they arise.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT

Arctic Sciences Section Planning

The research goal of the NSF Arctic Research Program is to gain a better understanding of the Earth's biological, geophysical, chemical, and sociocultural processes, and the interactions of ocean, land, atmosphere, biological, and human systems. The arctic regions are among the most sensitive to environmental change, and have exceptionally long natural climate records, and thousands of years of human settlement. This interplay provides a unique basis for integrated research on global systems and human adaptation.

ARCUS will develop information and communication resources that reach across geographic, cultural, institutional, and disciplinary barriers to assist planning and integration of these diverse research efforts and to improve awareness of NSF-sponsored research in the Arctic.

TASK 2.1: NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION INFORMATIONAL MATERIALS

The National Science Foundation has requested that ARCUS prepare a descriptive brochure for the Arctic Sciences Section of OPP designed for a general audience, including the public, policy makers, and personnel at NSF and other agencies. We propose to produce a brochure similar in scope and

audience to *Understanding Global Change in the Arctic: The National Science Foundation Arctic System Science Program*, which ARCUS published in 2000. The content of the new brochure, which would outline the activities and significance of the different programs of the Arctic Section, would also be developed into a poster suitable for display at scientific meetings.

The brochure will emphasize the special needs and opportunities of research in the Arctic, with a focus on the multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary research programs of the Arctic Section. Developing a broad understanding of the scientific justification for this regional approach to research will require concise information, comprehensible to non-scientists, about the purposes, accomplishments, and relevance of the various programs of the Arctic Section. In addition, the brochure will include information about the disciplinary programs supported by the Arctic Section including atmospheric sciences, biological sciences, earth sciences, glaciology, ocean sciences, and social sciences. Within social sciences, the brochure will emphasize recent research on long-term human/environment interactions and the study of contemporary socio-economic, cultural, and demographic issues in the changing arctic environment of the post-Cold War world.

The planned brochure also will cover the coordinated research efforts within NSF which support arctic research—both cooperation within OPP to support bipolar research (particularly glaciology, permafrost, sea ice, ecology, conjugate magnetic field lines, and human factors studies) as well as the links among disciplinary programs within the Foundation which coordinate arctic research across NSF. The purpose and accomplishments of the Arctic Research Support and Logistics Program in advancing arctic research efforts will be introduced as well. Finally, the brochure will briefly discuss the Arctic Section's responsibilities under the Arctic Research and Policy Act and outline

recent activities by the NSF in its role as the lead federal agency for arctic research.

In 2001, ARCUS will prepare, in consultation with the Arctic Section and OPP staff, a succinct brochure describing the recent activities and future research opportunities of the Arctic Section. ARCUS will prepare brochure content, coordinate the review process and final editing, and publish and print the brochure. ARCUS will make copies available to NSF for distribution and will distribute the brochure upon request.

2.2 Arctic System Science Program Planning and Coordination

The goal of the Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program is to understand the physical, chemical, biological, and social processes of the Arctic and how these arctic systems interact with the Earth as a whole. Developing this understanding, which is needed to predict global environmental change and to formulate policy options in response to these changes, requires organized multidisciplinary research. ARCUS proposes to support the continuing progress of the ARCSS Program through the following activities for the next five-year period:

Task 2.2.1: ARCSS COMMITTEE COORDINATION

ARCUS will continue to provide organizational support for the 13-member ARCSS Committee (AC), including coordinating the AC review of the accomplishments, priorities, and gaps in the various ARCSS components and projects and disseminating relevant information to the research community. ARCUS will convene one AC meeting per year, other work sessions of a sub-set of the committee as necessary, and provide staff support to the AC chair.

ARCUS will support the following major responsibilities of the AC:

- Articulate evolving criteria to evaluate component research programs and recommend priority areas,
- Assist ARCSS in evaluating and reviewing the progress of each research component,

- Assist with developing modeling and data management priorities,
- Serve as a conduit for new ARCSS community initiatives and assist in setting priorities among the emerging initiatives,
- Assist ARCSS in developing synthesis, integration, and modeling efforts.

Task 2.2.2: ARCSS ALL-INVESTIGATOR WORKSHOP

ARCUS will organize and support a second All-Investigator Workshop in 2002 to advance further both the interdisciplinary aspects and the system-science goals of the ARCSS program. The first ARCSS All-Investigator Workshop in 1996 gathered 175 scientists from the broad range of disciplines involved in ARCSS research. The interdisciplinary discussions among ARCSS principal investigators, co-investigators, graduate students, post-doctoral researchers, representatives of related research programs, and federal agency personnel developed a solid foundation for creating integrated, system-oriented science programs. Workshop participants viewed the significance of their research within the broader ARCSS Program, compared their diverse disciplines, methods, and perspectives, and discussed the steps necessary to move the ARCSS Program forward. By making their travel support a priority, graduate students and young investigators were encouraged to participate. ARCSS research efforts have become considerably more thematic and integrative across disciplinary and programmatic boundaries since 1996, in part because of the connections developed at the workshop among researchers from different disciplines.

The oral and poster presentations, recommendations from the working groups, and informal discussions during the meeting demonstrated ARCSS investigators' broad interest in the transition from science focused on individual components of the arctic system to integrated system science. The proceedings of the meeting are available in *Toward an Arctic System Synthesis: Results and Recommendations*, published by ARCUS

in 1998. The major accomplishment of this workshop was not, however, the production of this report, but the development of the integrative recommendations that formed the basis for the second ARCSS science plan, *Toward Prediction of the Arctic System*, published by ARCUS in 1998.

The focus and activities of the second All-Investigator workshop will be determined in deliberations with the AC, the ARCSS Program Director, and component and project science steering committees. The establishment of integrative linkages among scientists from different disciplines tasked with implementation of a visionary, system-based ARCSS research program requires facilitation of information exchange and interaction among participants. Partial and full support for travel will be used to reach a target of 250 participants. The AC has begun planning for the 2002 Workshop with the ARCSS research community, emphasizing a comprehensive evaluation of the Program's accomplishments, identification of important questions not currently being addressed by ARCSS research, and articulation of emergent research issues. The AC also recommends that the workshop include substantial provisions for the involvement of graduate students and post-doctoral fellows, by providing travel support and organizing sessions specifically for the contributions of young investigators.

TASK 2.2.X: ARCSS EDUCATION INITIATIVE

In addition to the extensive media coverage of the SHEBA Field Experiment in 1998, results from ARCSS-funded research have generated significant media interest in recent months, offering excellent opportunities for formal and informal science education at several levels. Although ARCSS investigators are already involved in a broad range of education and outreach activities to students, colleagues, arctic residents, and the general public, the ARCSS Committee has recommended that the ARCSS Program initiate a program-wide education effort to

maximize the effectiveness of these projects and has asked ARCUS to take the lead in this endeavor. In association with the 2002 All-Investigator Workshop, ARCUS will work with the community to develop a focus, strategy, and collaborations for an ARCSS-wide science education initiative to be proposed to the NSF Education and Human Resources Directorate and potentially to other funding entities. This initiative will bring together educators, researchers, and communities to use ARCSS research as the basis for a broad-based and coordinated educational program.

TASK 2.2.X: MODELING CD CURRICULUM PROJECT

An example of the type of educational project which is a natural extension of ARCSS-supported research is the *Arctic River Tracer Experiment CD*, developed by Wieslaw Maslowski of the Naval Postgraduate School as a means of making the animated results of his modeling research available to the research community. Dr. Maslowski has received many requests, however, for the CD from high school science

teachers for use in the classroom. ARCUS proposes to assist Maslowski in developing an educational version of the CD by adding appropriate narration to the animations

(Maslowski et al. 2000)

to provide context, background, and additional information suited to a high school audience. A primary educational focus would be demonstrating the use of modeling in the research process and helping students to understand the process of comparing retrospective modeling output to previous observational data sets and, conversely, how to use predictive models to plan a series of

field observations to answer key questions. This project could form the nucleus of a larger and more systematic educational effort bringing together the results from several ARCSS research efforts relevant to this area of research, such as the Western Arctic Shelf-Basins Interaction program. Adjunct curricular materials could be developed in the future in concert with this larger project, including materials to teach students to develop and use simple models. Curriculum specialists would participate in the development of these resources to assure that the program addressed the relevant educational standards.

2.3 Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination

Scientists, policy makers, educators, and indigenous peoples recognize the importance of the Arctic in social science research (*Arctic Contributions to Social Science and Public Policy* 1993, *Arctic Social Sciences: Opportunities in Arctic Research* 1999). The circumpolar North offers excellent research opportunities to social scientists, regardless of their discipline or time period of interest, but taking advantage of these opportunities requires a network to facilitate communication across political, cultural, and scientific boundaries.

Well-established links with the global arctic community put ARCUS in an excellent position to connect and synthesize diverse perspectives and ideas about basic research in the social sciences for the benefit of arctic research generally.

TASK 2.3.1: ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES WORKSHOP

ARCUS has begun organizing a forum and process for information exchange about findings, gaps, and priorities in current arctic social sciences research. This planning process, initiated at the request of the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program, is intended to generate new ideas and inform the broader social science community about

arctic research opportunities by including participants from several disciplinary, cultural, and geographic communities.

An international organizing committee of social scientists conducting research in the Arctic, jointly established by the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program Manager, the Polar Research Board, and ARCUS in 2000, recommended that this phased planning process should begin with a three-day planning workshop in January 2001 to consider needs and priorities, followed by either a larger arctic social sciences conference or a series of focused workshops. The January 2001 planning workshop is funded through ARCUS' current cooperative agreement with NSF. The follow-on workshops or conference, tentatively scheduled for the fall of 2001, are included in this proposal. This workshop and conference series is intended to generate new ideas and inform the broader social science community about arctic research opportunities by including participants from several disciplinary, cultural, and geographic communities.

In addition to arctic social scientists, participants will include social scientists working outside the Arctic, agency managers whose mandates include social science research, graduate students in social sciences and related interdisciplinary research, and researchers in other fields relevant to social sciences.

The ultimate goals of this planning and information exchange process are to:

- generate increased awareness in relevant communities (agency representatives, social science researchers, other researchers whose work intersects the social sciences, and young investigators, especially those who are working in interdisciplinary areas) of opportunities for innovative social science research in the Arctic,
- provide models of social science contributions to human dimensions questions,
- focus attention on priority or emerging areas of arctic social science.

Workshop themes will include:

- the role of humans in northern environmental history and pre-history;
- institutional development in the Arctic, such as self-governance, common property management, and informal decision-making;
- linkages between identity and socioeconomic transitions in the Arctic; and
- traditional knowledge and the intersection between the social sciences and the humanities.

After exchanging recent research results, pinpointing promising intersections between social science questions and other disciplines, and identifying urgent research problems and the impediments to addressing those problems, the January 2001 workshop attendees will determine the steps necessary to address the needs and priorities they identify, in the context of a community-wide arctic social sciences conference, several smaller workshops on specific focused topics, or other activities yet to be determined.

TASK 2.3.2: TRANSLATION AND PUBLICATION OF *DEN NYE SIKKERHED - GROENLAND I ET SIKKERHEDSPOLITISK PERSPEKTIV* (THE NEW SECURITY: GREENLAND IN A SECURITY POLITICAL PERSPECTIVE)

Den Nye Sikkerhed was published in Danish in 1999 and, because of the increasing interest from the U.S. research community in conducting research in Greenland, an English version has been recommended. Updated from a 1982 edition, the book contains information about Greenland's history, economy, politics, geography, environment, resources, laws, and the U.S. presence there. This publication will serve as a resource for researchers planning to work in Greenland and for others interested in background information about the country and its evolution.

A translator has been identified and the authors are currently adding and updating information. To prepare and publish the English translation, ARCUS will coordinate

translation of the 80-page book from Danish to English, prepare document contents and graphics in publication layout, copy-edit and coordinate printing and distribution of the document.

TASK 2.3.X: TRAVEL SUPPORT FOR ICASS IV (THE INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS OF ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES)

ARCUS will provide limited travel support for 20 participants from the United States and Russia to attend the fourth International Congress of Arctic Social Scientists (ICASS IV), sponsored by the International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA), from 16-20 May 2001 in Quebec City, Canada. Travel support will be prioritized to provide opportunities to participate in this international conference to students, post-doctoral fellows, and independent scholars.

2.4 Arctic Natural Sciences Program Planning and Coordination

TASK 2.4.1: ARCTIC NATURAL SCIENCES SECTION INFORMATIONAL MATERIALS

The Arctic Natural Sciences (ANS) Program is a multidisciplinary program within the NSF Office of Polar Programs (OPP) Arctic Sciences Section that supports research in the atmospheric sciences, biological sciences, earth sciences, glaciology, and oceanography. The ANS Program provides core support for disciplinary research in the Arctic and coordinates arctic research with the NSF Directorates for Geosciences and Biological Sciences. Additionally, the program helps facilitate OPP multidisciplinary, cross-disciplinary and bipolar projects. Areas of special interest include ozone depletion in the Arctic, space weather, exploration of the Arctic Ocean, and environmental processes.

ARCUS will prepare, in consultation with the ANS staff, a succinct brochure describing the recent activities and future research opportunities of the program. These informational materials will be designed for a general audience, including the public, policy makers, and personnel at NSF and other agencies. We propose to produce a brochure similar in scope and audience to *Understanding Global Change in the Arctic: The National Science Foundation Arctic System Science Program*, which ARCUS published in 2000. The content of the ANS brochure, which would outline the activities and significance of the research supported by the program, would also be developed into a poster suitable for display at scientific meetings.

ARCUS will develop brochure content, coordinate the review process and final editing, and publish and print the brochure. ARCUS will make copies available to NSF for distribution and will distribute the brochure upon request.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

Educational leadership activities are important to the NSF, and to arctic research, not only to improve scientific programs, but to improve the science literacy of the nation. ARCUS will continue to play an educational leadership role within the arctic community to improve the quality of scientific research and to increase public understanding of and appreciation for science and the Arctic.

A major goal of science education focused on the Arctic is to increase the awareness of arctic scientific research within the public and in K-12 schools, while teaching fundamental scientific concepts. ARCUS has been working towards this goal for the past eight years; several educational activities funded by NSF are highlighted on pages 6-7, Results from Prior NSF Support. ARCUS also leads several science education efforts sponsored by other organizations. Although not described here, information about these other science education projects is available on the ARCUS web site.

TASK 3.1: ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION PROGRAM COORDINATION AND DIRECTORY

The major recommendation of the March 2000 Arctic Science Education Working Group convened by ARCUS was the creation of a geographically dispersed set of coordinating infrastructures to link the many ongoing science education efforts in the Arctic and to establish long-term effective partnerships among arctic researchers,

educators, schools, students, and communities. ARCUS has functioned effectively as a neutral and central information and coordination hub and has provided leadership in the ongoing

development of many innovative and effective science education programs now underway in the Arctic. ARCUS is now in an excellent position to assist the Office of Polar Programs in the development of broad-based science education efforts, building strong partnerships with the research and education communities and with the NSF Education and Human Resources Directorate (EHR). ARCUS will provide important links with arctic efforts, such as developing K-12 education programs, improving public understanding of science, and the involvement of indigenous peoples, with the broader educational goals of OPP. Proposed activities will include:

- Infrastructure and coordination support for science education collaborations initiated by researchers and educators. Support may range from connecting interested teachers, researchers, students, and arctic residents, to providing

detailed logistical support, depending on the individual needs of the project.

- Development of an on-line Arctic Science Education Directory that will connect the arctic research and education communities ARCUS serves to important human and programmatic resources. The Arctic Science Education directory will include teachers, indigenous people, curriculum developers, and scientists interested in participating in arctic science education projects. In addition, this directory will catalog arctic science education materials available, including activities, curricula, and related web sites. This directory will allow ARCUS to play a key coordinating and "matchmaking" role in specific educational initiatives. It will also promote the development of important relationships between arctic researchers and arctic communities, an important aspect of arctic science education. ARCUS has established sound, flexible, and effective survey and directory development procedures that will serve well in this endeavor.
- ARCUS proposes to assist OPP in initiating and developing educational programs, following on the recommendations developed at the April 1997 Arctic Science Education Workshop and the March 2000 Arctic Science Education Working Group. Activities will include facilitating development of educational resources using data from and research participation with OPP-funded projects.

TASK 3.2: ARCTIC VISITING SPEAKERS SERIES

The investigators who make up the arctic research community are diverse in their interests and distributed geographically. Collaboration and knowledge sharing are possible through workshops and conferences, as well as through traveling speakers programs. A few interdisciplinary arctic science meetings (the *Arctic Forum*, hosted by ARCUS, and the Arctic Science Conference, sponsored by AAAS) bring members of the community together, but most scientific

meetings are disciplinary and few address the specific interests of arctic communities. ARCUS initiated the Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture better understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents. The AVS was fully subscribed in 2000, and community feedback and interest in the program indicates that it fills a previously unmet need. We propose to continue the visiting speakers series at a modest level, sponsoring up to 15 speakers each year over the next five years.

This cost-effective means for improving interactions among individual researchers and institutions engaged in arctic research also will help promote productive collaborations among disciplines and between researchers and arctic communities and broaden the educational opportunities available to students interested in arctic research. Funding at many academic institutions for these educational endeavors has decreased in recent years despite the demonstrated value of such interactions, particularly to institutions in more remote locations. Few communities have the resources to invite arctic scientists or experts on the Arctic to interact with elementary and secondary schools and the public. A developing Speakers Bureau of distinguished arctic researchers, policymakers, and educators is available on the ARCUS Web site.

ARCUS regularly announces the availability of the program via Arctic Info, which reaches more than 3,100 arctic researchers, policymakers, and residents of arctic communities. The schedule of visiting speakers and host institutions is posted on the ARCUS web site and announced in *Witness the Arctic* to increase the visibility of the program and honor the speakers. Presentations are videotaped, when possible, and may be converted to DVD ROM. Each annual series, on VHS or DVD media, will be available for education and information purposes.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

ARCUS represents the majority of U.S. academic and research institutions involved in arctic research. As such, ARCUS serves as a communication channel, providing information about current research activities and arctic issues to the scientific community as well as to agencies and the public. To be effective, this must be done at a number of levels, including non-technical communication, newsletters, electronic communications, forums like the ARCUS-sponsored *Arctic Forum*, and workshops. Six of the following tasks describe specific activities through which ARCUS provides information to arctic researchers, policy and decision-makers, residents of arctic communities and the public. The seventh task describes a set of outreach activities that are flexibly responsive to community needs and emerging priorities in arctic research.

TASK 4.1: WITNESS THE ARCTIC: CHRONICLES OF THE NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES PROGRAM

ARCUS receives praise from readers representing many communities for *Witness the Arctic* for its valuable news, updates, and information and for its broad coverage. Each issue of *Witness* contains news of interest to scientists from a wide variety of disciplines and the public and is read by more than 6,500 national and international subscribers, including arctic scientists and engineers, educators, students, agency personnel, and interested members of the public. The newsletter strives to make current arctic research developments accessible to both scientists and the public. In addition to thorough coverage of a broad spectrum of lead stories, *Witness* provides information about each of the programs of the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, and other programs and issues of interest to researchers including:

- planning updates for major research initiatives and programs,
- information relevant to national and international arctic policy matters,

- innovative arctic science education activities,
- relevant national and international research and coordination efforts,
- Arctic science activities of U.S. universities and research institutes.

ARCUS proposes to continue publishing a 28-32 page issue of *Witness* twice annually, in the spring and fall, in an on-line and a print edition.

TASK 4.2: ARCUS INTERNET RESOURCES

ARCUS maintains a web site with information important to the arctic research community, links to many arctic research efforts' sites, links to relevant publications and organizations, a searchable Arctic Info archive, a calendar of events, and a searchable directory of arctic researchers. All ARCUS publications are available on-line through the web site. Maintaining and updating this complex site requires a substantial amount of effort. The site receives several thousand hits per week.

A total redesign of the site began in fall 2000 to take advantage of new software and hardware capability, while retaining the features applauded by the research community and other users. Development efforts include designing a more visually appealing

site with an improved navigation system. New technologies also allow a more interactive user experience. New features include better site search, site map, and index func-

tions and improvements to the dynamic database that organizes links, publications, scientific and corporate committees, and other important information. Database

functions will be converted to take advantage of the newest XML developments, which will decrease download times, increase the perceived response time for the end user, and display data in a client-side sortable format. Increasing bandwidth and upgrading server capacity will increase the number of arctic researchers able to access the ARCUS web site at any given time and the speed with which publications and other information can be viewed or downloaded.

TASK 4.3: ARCTIC INFO LISTSERVER

ARCUS proposes to continue developing and maintaining Arctic Info, the primary email listserver for the arctic research community. Arctic Info provides timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position announcements, and other useful news. Unlike many listservers, messages are not allowed to post to Arctic Info automatically, in order to assure relevance of the information to subscribers and to reduce the nuisance of inappropriate or ill-conceived messages. Prior to distribution, all postings are reviewed for appropriateness, information is checked for accuracy, and, in some cases, messages are edited for formatting and content. Changes are submitted to the sender for approval before posting. Management of the listserver is time-intensive and requires comprehension of arctic research issues, as well as excellent editorial skills.

All postings are archived in a searchable directory on the ARCUS web site. Over 3,100 researchers currently subscribe to Arctic Info and the subscription list grows daily. More than 530 announcements have been posted since the listserver was initiated in 1996.

TASK 4.4: DIRECTORY OF ARCTIC RESEARCHERS

The *Directory of Arctic Researchers* was initiated in 1994 to facilitate networking and collaboration in arctic research and education efforts between individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders. The contents of the *Directory*,

which includes U.S. and international arctic researchers, are developed through surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions. The directory now contains over 2,800 researchers and is available as a searchable database at the ARCUS web site with simple and complex search capabilities by scientific specialty and basic contact information. The directory and disciplinary cross-reference are available on the web site as PDF files.

ARCUS proposes to continue maintenance and expansion of the on-line version of the directory. A major expansion of the directory was initiated in 1999 to include non-U.S. arctic researchers, to support the development of international collaborations and multi-national development of logistics resources. Approximately 1,100 of the researchers added since 1999 have been from outside the U.S. Users now have requested that we expand the directory to include arctic science administrators at Alaska State agencies, federal agencies, and international research organizations.

Hardware and software will be upgraded to keep pace with information technology improvements, including added server equipment and new software to increase the size, speed, accessibility, and search capability of the on-line directory. Upgrades may involve switching the on-line directory to a different database backbone allowing better dynamic on-line search functions and increased search speed and efficiency of updating data.

Directory search features now allow concatenated searches, either/or selections, text string searches, and complex search combinations, which we will continue to refine, as well as developing the dynamic generation of PDF files to allow full on-line generation of either the total directory or discrete sections by specific search criteria.

TASK 4.5: INTERNET GRAPHICS ARCHIVE

ARCUS was funded in 2000 through the current cooperative agreement with NSF to develop a graphics archive depicting arctic

TASK 4.6: ARCTIC COMMUNITY OUTREACH

ARCUS makes a valuable contribution to the arctic research community by bringing individuals and groups together for collaboration and information sharing that transcends disciplinary, geographical, and governmental boundaries.

The annual interdisciplinary *Arctic Forum* is an important outreach activity sponsored by ARCUS and is typically attended by more than 100 participants. Held each year since 1994 in conjunction with ARCUS annual meeting, the *Forum* brings together investigators, federal agency officials and students for presentations on new and cutting-edge arctic research, resulting in important contacts and collaborations among researchers, agencies, and countries. The proceedings of the *Arctic Forum* are published in an abstract volume. Other outreach activities to be continued in response to emerging needs and priorities include:

- Promoting collaborative efforts among institutions and organizations, focused at the technical training, college, and university levels, to ensure that a technical and scientific work force is available to meet national needs in the Arctic;
- Working with research institutions, the public, and funding agencies to identify new areas where broad-based, integrative research efforts are needed in the Arctic;
- Working with Native organizations in the Arctic and scientists to develop effective means by which results of NSF-funded research can be returned to northern communities.
- Making information available through meetings, reports, and other media to policy and decision makers to incorporate

important scientific questions and results into legislative agendas;

- Facilitating discussion and collaboration between federal agency and university-based researchers to meet the needs of both in arctic research, education, and outreach;
- Providing information on research, research-related events, and research institutions in the Arctic to the general public through forums, the news media, the Internet, and various publications to increase the public's understanding of the significance of scientific research;
- Responding to ongoing requests for information on the Arctic, and on arctic research programs, efforts, resources and logistical support opportunities.

5. CORE SUPPORT

ARCUS has included a category called Core Support in the task descriptions, at the suggestion of NSF, to describe and capture costs incurred that relate to and support multiple NSF projects and tasks. Items included in Core Support include:

- Salaries and benefits of the Executive Director for general supervision over all NSF tasks;
- Hardware and software technology to provide particular capability required of multiple NSF tasks (For example, the ability to deliver information from a database over a website will be used for the *Directory of Arctic Researchers*, the ALIAS web site, the Graphics Archive and other tasks. This capability is not required of non-NSF projects at ARCUS);
- Communications requirements specifically needed to support NSF tasks;
- Salaries and benefits for the systems administrator when supporting capabilities required by multiple NSF tasks;
- Staff training for NSF-specific capabilities;
- Staff travel to conferences and meetings to maintain necessary level of involvement and knowledge of NSF arctic science interests, but not particular to one task.

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- Toward Prediction of the Arctic System: Predicting States of the Arctic System on Seasonal-to-century Time Scales by Integrating Observations, Process Research, Modeling, and Assessment*. 1998. ARCUS: Fairbanks, Alaska. 54 pp.
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- Witness the Arctic*. 1993-2000. Fairbanks, Alaska: ARCUS. Vol. 1-8, various pp.

BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH FOR WENDY K. WARNICK**PROFESSIONAL PREPARATION:**

N/A

APPOINTMENTS:

1994 to present - Executive Director, Arctic Research Consortium of the United States

1997 to present - Ex-officio member of the ARCUS Board of Directors

1992 to 1994 - Program Manager, Arctic Research Consortium of the United States

Prior to 1992 - Twenty years experience in planning, coordination, program administration, community health and policy education, and Arctic issues, including:

- Executive Director, Interior Alaska Economic Development Council
- Executive Director, Child, Adolescent, and Family Services, Fairbanks Community Mental Health Center
- Consultant/Trainer/Instructor, (1) State of Alaska Department of Public Safety; (2) State of Alaska Division of Mental Health and Developmental Disabilities; (3) various Alaskan communities, and national and state non-profit organizations
- Program Director, Alaska Northern Region Child Sexual Abuse Task Force
- Renewable Energy and Appropriate Technology Consultant, Northern Alaska Environmental Center
- Assistant Manager, University of Alaska Musk Ox Project

PUBLICATIONS:**(i) A list of up to 5 publications most closely related to the proposed project.**

Co-author or managing editor of the following publications published by ARCUS:

Building Partnerships in Polar Research and Education. Report from the Arctic Science Education Workshop, April 1997, New Orleans, Louisiana. 1998. ARCUS: Fairbanks, Alaska. 35 pp.

The Future of an Arctic Resource: Recommendations from the Barrow Area Research Support Workshop. 1999.

ARCUS: Fairbanks, Alaska. 104 pp.

Opportunities for Collaboration Between the United States and Norway in Arctic Research: A Workshop Report. 2000.

ARCUS: Fairbanks, Alaska. 91 pp.

People and the Arctic: A Prospectus for Research on the Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC Prospectus). 1997.

ARCUS: Fairbanks, Alaska. 75 pp.

Schlosser, P., W. Tucker, N. Flanders, and W. Warnick. 1997. *Logistics Recommendations for an Improved U.S. Arctic Research Capability.* ARCUS: Fairbanks, Alaska. 88 pp.

(ii) A list of up to 5 other significant publications, whether or not related to the proposed project.

Managing editor of the following publications published by ARCUS:

Modeling the Arctic System: A Workshop Report on the State of Modeling in the Arctic System Science Program. 1997.

ARCUS: Fairbanks, Alaska. 141 pp.

Toolik Field Station: The Second Twenty Years. Recommendations on the science mission and the development of Toolik Field Station. 1996. ARCUS: Fairbanks, Alaska. 35 pp.

Toward Prediction of the Arctic System: Predicting States of the Arctic System on Seasonal-to-century Time Scales by Integrating Observations, Process Research, Modeling, and Assessment. 1998. ARCUS: Fairbanks, Alaska. 54 pp.

Understanding Global Change in the Arctic: the National Science Foundation Arctic System Science Program. 2000. ARCUS: Fairbanks, AK. Brochure.

Witness the Arctic. 1993-2000. Fairbanks, Alaska: ARCUS. Vol. 1-8, various pp.

SYNERGISTIC ACTIVITIES:

- Coordinates interdisciplinary, integrative scientific planning and supervises preparation of synthesis reports.
- Identifies individuals in the research community appropriate for various forms of collaboration on a formal and informal basis.
- Conceived and developed the Directory of Arctic Researchers which has facilitated countless collaborations.
- Facilitated development and implementation of education project mentoring students with disabilities for careers in math, science, and engineering in the Arctic.
- Works to broaden outreach to Alaska native community through education programs and integration of Traditional Knowledge into programs of ARCUS.
- Encourages young researchers through implementation of ARCUS student award program.

COLLABORATIONS:

While Ms. Warnick works extensively with a large number of arctic researchers, educators, and indigenous peoples representatives she has not been a collaborator on a proposal with anyone in the past 48 months.

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-mos.		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	10.80	0.00	0.00	\$	69,264	\$	
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00		0		
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	10.80	0.00	0.00		69,264		
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00		0		
2. (7) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	70.62	0.00	0.00		276,432		
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS					0		
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS					0		
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)					38,584		
6. (0) OTHER					0		
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					384,280		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					122,970		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					507,250		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					0		
E. TRAVEL					82,793		
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN					2,366		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS	\$	20,000					
2. TRAVEL		74,800					
3. SUBSISTENCE		38,226					
4. OTHER		0					
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (86)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS	133,026		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES					46,810		
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION					131,264		
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES					33,000		
4. COMPUTER SERVICES					500		
5. SUBAWARDS					0		
6. OTHER					37,435		
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					249,009		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					974,444		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect (Rate: 42.1000, Base: 974444)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					410,240		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					1,384,684		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)					\$ 1,384,684	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI / PD TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	FOR NSF USE ONLY			
Wendy K Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 2

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-mos.		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	10.80	0.00	0.00	\$ 73,008			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	10.80	0.00	0.00	73,008			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (7) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	61.12	0.00	0.00	254,351			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				40,560			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)				367,919			
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)				117,734			
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)				485,653			
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT				0			
E. TRAVEL				74,908			
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN				2,366			
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$	13,000						
2. TRAVEL	106,800						
3. SUBSISTENCE	64,311						
4. OTHER	0						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS	(126)	TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS		184,111			
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				47,210			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				91,258			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				21,200			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				500			
5. SUBAWARDS				0			
6. OTHER				51,575			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS				211,743			
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)				958,781			
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect (Rate: 42.1000, Base: 958781)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)				403,646			
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)				1,362,427			
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)				0			
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				\$ 1,362,427	\$		
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI / PD TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE* Wendy K Warnick			DATE	FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
				Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 3

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-mos.		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	10.80	0.00	0.00	\$ 76,752			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	10.80	0.00	0.00	76,752			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (7) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	54.10	0.00	0.00	238,026			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				42,536			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)				357,314			
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)				471,654			
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							
				0			
E. TRAVEL							
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)				64,881			
2. FOREIGN				2,403			
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$	13,000						
2. TRAVEL	80,700						
3. SUBSISTENCE	44,886						
4. OTHER	0						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (91)	TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS			138,586			
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				46,860			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				65,984			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				14,900			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				500			
5. SUBAWARDS				0			
6. OTHER				39,285			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS				167,529			
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							
				845,053			
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
Indirect (Rate: 42.1000, Base: 845053)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)				355,767			
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							
				1,200,820			
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)							
				0			
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							
				\$ 1,200,820			
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0 AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$							
PI / PD TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	FOR NSF USE ONLY			
Wendy K Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET

YEAR 4

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-mos.		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	10.80	0.00	0.00	\$	80,496	\$	
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00		0		
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	10.80	0.00	0.00		80,496		
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00		0		
2. (7) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	53.30	0.00	0.00		246,150		
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS					0		
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS					0		
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)					44,512		
6. (0) OTHER					0		
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					371,158		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					118,771		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					489,929		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT						0	
E. TRAVEL					65,894		
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN					2,441		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS	\$	13,000					
2. TRAVEL		82,600					
3. SUBSISTENCE		44,886					
4. OTHER		0					
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (91)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS	140,486		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES					46,860		
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION					65,984		
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES					15,000		
4. COMPUTER SERVICES					500		
5. SUBAWARDS					0		
6. OTHER					39,285		
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					167,629		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					866,379		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
Indirect (Rate: 42.1000, Base: 866379)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					364,745		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					1,231,124		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)					\$ 1,231,124	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI / PD TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	FOR NSF USE ONLY			
Wendy K Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 5

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-mos.		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	10.80	0.00	0.00	\$ 84,708			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	10.80	0.00	0.00	84,708			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (7) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	57.34	0.00	0.00	276,530			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
5. (2) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				46,488			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)				407,726			
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)				130,472			
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)				538,198			
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT				0			
E. TRAVEL							
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)				66,906			
2. FOREIGN				2,478			
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$	13,000						
2. TRAVEL	84,500						
3. SUBSISTENCE	44,886						
4. OTHER	0						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (91)				142,386			
TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				46,860			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				89,584			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				17,000			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				500			
5. SUBAWARDS				0			
6. OTHER				39,285			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS				193,229			
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)				943,197			
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect (Rate: 42.1000, Base: 943197)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)				397,085			
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)				1,340,282			
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)				0			
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				\$ 1,340,282			
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI / PD TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	FOR NSF USE ONLY			
Wendy K Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-mos.		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
		CAL	ACAD	SUMR			
1.	Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	54.00	0.00	0.00	\$ 384,228	\$	
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6.	() OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0		
7.	(1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	54.00	0.00	0.00	384,228		
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1.	(0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0		
2.	(35) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	296.48	0.00	0.00	1,291,489		
3.	(0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0		
4.	(0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				0		
5.	(10) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				212,680		
6.	(0) OTHER				0		
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					1,888,397		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					604,287		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					2,492,684		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					0		
E. TRAVEL					355,382		
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN					12,054		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1.	STIPENDS \$ _____	72,000					
2.	TRAVEL _____	429,400					
3.	SUBSISTENCE _____	237,195					
4.	OTHER _____	0					
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (485)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS	738,595		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES					234,600		
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION					444,074		
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES					101,100		
4. COMPUTER SERVICES					2,500		
5. SUBAWARDS					0		
6. OTHER					206,865		
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					989,139		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					4,587,854		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					1,931,486		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					6,519,340		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.D.7.j.)					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)					\$ 6,519,340	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI / PD TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	FOR NSF USE ONLY			
Wendy K Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
ORG. REP. TYPED NAME & SIGNATURE*			DATE	Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION BY TASK - Proposal #1089925

	<u>2001</u>	<u>2002</u>	<u>2003</u>	<u>2004</u>	<u>2005</u>	<u>Total</u>
1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING						
1.1 Logistics Planning						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	25,733	18,601	16,535	17,249	31,904	110,023
Travel (domestic)	6,308	6,308	6,408	6,508	6,608	32,140
Participant Support Costs	32,344	32,344	32,994	33,644	34,294	165,620
Materials and Supplies	260	260	260	260	260	1,300
Publications/Dissemination	24,010	8,910	416	416	24,016	57,767
Consulting	1,000	-	-	-	1,000	2,000
Other Direct Costs	4,320	4,320	4,320	4,320	4,320	21,600
Total direct costs	93,975	70,743	60,933	62,397	102,402	390,450
1.2 ALIAS/Logistics Internet Resources						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	69,082	73,960	77,598	81,510	85,611	387,760
Travel (domestic)	15,770	15,770	16,020	16,270	16,520	80,350
Consulting	10,000	-	-	-	-	10,000
Other Direct Costs	1,500	100	100	100	100	1,900
Total direct costs	96,352	89,830	93,718	97,880	102,231	480,010
1.3 Arctic GIS Planning						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,282	-	-	-	-	13,282
Participant Support Costs	7,000	-	-	-	-	7,000
Publications/Dissemination	29,800	-	-	-	-	29,800
Total direct costs	50,082	-	-	-	-	50,082
1.4-1.6 Workshop/Report Contingency						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	-	16,535	17,249	18,118	51,902
Travel (domestic)	-	-	3,204	3,254	3,304	9,762
Participant Support Costs	-	-	31,725	32,350	32,975	97,050
Materials and Supplies	-	-	250	250	250	750
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	9,700	9,700	9,700	29,100
Other Direct Costs	-	-	3,500	3,500	3,500	10,500
Total direct costs	-	-	64,914	66,303	67,847	199,064
Subtotal Community Planning	240,409	160,573	219,565	226,580	272,480	1,119,606
2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION						
2.1 Arctic Section Science Materials						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	13,281.8	-	-	-	-	13,282
Publications/Dissemination	11,500.0	-	-	-	-	11,500
Total direct costs	24,782	-	-	-	-	24,782
2.2 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION						
8 2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	11,046	11,573	12,100	12,223	13,257	60,199
Travel (domestic)	5,520	5,520	5,607	5,695	5,782	28,123
Participant Support Costs	23,550	23,550	23,800	24,050	24,300	119,250
Materials and Supplies	100	100	100	100	100	500
Publications/Dissemination	258	158	160	160	160	895
Other Direct Costs	3,340	3,340	3,340	3,340	3,340	16,700
Total direct costs	43,813	44,240	45,107	45,568	46,939	225,666

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION BY TASK - Proposal #1089925

	<u>2001</u>	<u>2002</u>	<u>2003</u>	<u>2004</u>	<u>2005</u>	<u>Total</u>
<u>2.2.2 ARCSS All-Investigator Workshop</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	28,499	26,893	-	-	6,629	62,021
Travel (domestic)	-	6,308	-	-	-	6,308
Participant Support Costs	-	47,425	-	-	-	47,425
Materials and Supplies	-	350	-	-	-	350
Publications/Dissemination	-	10,500	-	-	-	10,500
Consulting	4,000	4,000	-	-	-	8,000
Other Direct Costs	250	12,250	-	-	-	12,500
Total direct costs	32,749	107,726	-	-	6,629	147,104
<u>2.2.X ARCSS Education Initiative</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	9,884	-	-	-	-	9,884
Total direct costs	9,884	-	-	-	-	9,884
<u>2.2.X ARCSS CD Curriculum Project</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	9,884	-	-	-	-	9,884
Total direct costs	9,884	-	-	-	-	9,884
Subtotal ARCSS	96,330	151,966	45,107	45,568	53,568	392,539
<u>2.3 ASSP PROGRAM COORDINATION</u>						
<u>2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Workshop</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	15,822	-	-	-	15,822
Travel (domestic)	-	3,154	-	-	-	3,154
Participant Support Costs	-	31,100	-	-	-	31,100
Materials and Supplies	-	250	-	-	-	250
Publications/Dissemination	-	7,694	-	-	-	7,694
Consulting	-	2,500	-	-	-	2,500
Other Direct Costs	-	3,540	-	-	-	3,540
Total direct costs	-	64,059	-	-	-	64,059
<u>2.3.2 Greenland Book Translation</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	6,043	-	-	-	-	6,043
Publications/Dissemination	10,000	-	-	-	-	10,000
Consulting	3,500	-	-	-	-	3,500
Total direct costs	19,543	-	-	-	-	19,543
<u>2.3.X IASSA Travel</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,888	-	-	-	-	2,888
Participant Support Costs	20,440	-	-	-	-	20,440
Materials and Supplies	200	-	-	-	-	200
Total direct costs	23,528	-	-	-	-	23,528
Subtotal ASSP	43,071	64,059	-	-	-	107,131

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION BY TASK - Proposal #1089925

	<u>2001</u>	<u>2002</u>	<u>2003</u>	<u>2004</u>	<u>2005</u>	<u>Total</u>
2.4 ANS PROGRAM COORDINATION						
2.4.1 ANS science materials						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-	10,193	-	-	-	10,193
Publications/Dissemination	-	8,300	-	-	-	8,300
Total direct costs	-	18,493	-	-	-	18,493
Subtotal Arctic Sciences Section	164,183	234,518	45,107	45,568	53,568	542,944
3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION						
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	2,656	2,595	2,718	2,842	2,965	13,776
Travel (domestic)	3,154	3,154	3,204	3,254	3,304	16,070
Participant Support Costs	3,732	3,732	3,807	3,882	3,957	19,110
Materials and Supplies	250	250	250	250	250	1,250
Publications/Dissemination	47	47	48	48	48	239
Consulting	5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000	25,000
Total direct costs	14,840	14,778	15,027	15,276	15,524	75,445
3.2 Visiting Speakers Series						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	4,942	5,189	5,436	5,683	5,930	27,181
Participant Support Costs	29,700	29,700	29,700	29,700	29,700	148,500
Total direct costs	34,642	34,889	35,136	35,383	35,630	175,681
Subtotal Education	49,482	49,667	50,163	50,659	51,155	251,126
4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH						
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	17,034	17,833	18,632	19,431	20,415	93,344
Travel (domestic)	1,577	1,577	1,602	1,627	1,652	8,035
Materials and Supplies	100	100	100	100	100	500
Publications/Dissemination	40,200	40,200	40,200	40,200	40,200	201,000
Total direct costs	58,911	59,710	60,534	61,358	62,367	302,879
4.2 Arctic Internet Resources						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	67,356	70,843	74,330	78,078	81,956	372,564
Total direct costs	67,356	70,843	74,330	78,078	81,956	372,564
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	18,039	18,883	19,727	20,571	21,570	98,790
Total direct costs	18,039	18,883	19,727	20,571	21,570	98,790
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	5,477	5,766	6,054	6,342	6,631	30,270
Travel (domestic)	1,577	1,577	1,602	1,627	1,652	8,035
Consulting	-	-	-	-	1,000	1,000
Total direct costs	7,054	7,343	7,656	7,969	9,283	39,305

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION BY TASK - Proposal #1089925

	<u>2001</u>	<u>2002</u>	<u>2003</u>	<u>2004</u>	<u>2005</u>	<u>Total</u>
4.5 Internet Graphics Archive						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	8,855	7,413	9,678	6,054	10,605	42,605
Publications/Dissemination	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	12,500
Consulting	5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000	25,000
Total direct costs	16,355	14,913	17,178	13,554	18,105	80,105
4.X Fastlane Training for Rural Alaska						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	7,413	3,114	-	-	-	10,527
Travel (domestic)	14,193	4,731	-	-	-	18,924
Total direct costs	21,606	7,845	-	-	-	29,451
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	10,857	11,930	11,890	12,406	13,027	60,110
Travel (domestic)	9,462	9,462	9,612	9,762	9,912	48,210
Participant Support Costs	16,260	16,260	16,560	16,860	17,160	83,100
Materials and Supplies	400	400	400	400	400	2,000
Publications/Dissemination	8,130	8,130	8,140	8,140	8,140	40,680
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	14,000	14,000	14,000	14,000	14,000	70,000
Total direct costs	59,109	60,182	60,602	61,568	62,639	304,100
Subtotal Info and Outreach	248,430	239,718	240,027	243,098	255,920	1,227,194
5. CORE SUPPORT						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	174,996	185,047	200,421	210,290	219,581	990,334
Travel (domestic/foreign)	27,598	19,713	20,025	20,338	20,650	108,323
Materials and supplies	45,500	45,500	45,500	45,500	45,500	227,500
Publications/Dissemination	4,820	4,820	4,820	4,820	4,820	24,100
Consulting	4,500	4,700	4,900	5,000	5,000	24,100
Computer Services	500	500	500	500	500	2,500
Other Direct Costs	14,025	14,025	14,025	14,025	14,025	70,125
Total direct costs	271,939	274,304	290,191	300,472	310,076	1,446,981
<u>TOTAL</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	507,250	485,653	471,654	489,929	538,199	2,492,684
Travel	85,158	77,273	67,284	68,334	69,384	367,433
Participant Support Costs	133,026	184,111	138,586	140,486	142,386	738,595
Materials and Supplies	46,810	47,210	46,860	46,860	46,860	234,600
Publications/Dissemination	131,264	91,258	65,984	65,984	89,584	444,074
Consulting	33,000	21,200	14,900	15,000	17,000	101,100
Computer Services	500	500	500	500	500	2,500
Other Direct Costs	37,435	51,575	39,285	39,285	39,285	206,865
Total direct costs	974,443	958,780	845,053	866,378	943,198	4,587,852
Indirect Costs @ 42.1%	410,240	403,646	355,767	364,745	397,086	1,931,485
Total direct and indirect	1,384,683	1,362,426	1,200,821	1,231,123	1,340,284	6,519,337

BUDGET EXPLANATION FOR PROPOSAL #1089925

EXPLANATION OF SIGNIFICANT COSTS

TASK 5: CORE SUPPORT

All costs charged to core support are for items directly benefiting multiple NSF tasks. Salaries and fringe are for that portion of time the Executive Director, Systems Administrator and the Executive Assistant contribute to supervision and work supporting more than one task. Travel will pay for staff to attend science meetings and training necessary to support the NSF effort. Materials and supplies pay for computer hardware and software (items costing less than \$5,000) that are used in direct support of NSF tasks. Publication and dissemination will cover postage for continued distribution of NSF-funded publications after the initial dissemination. Consulting fees are for the single audit required by NSF. Computer services will pay for special services to support Internet intensive tasks. Other direct costs include special communications needs and conference and training fees to support staff attendance at science meetings and technical training.

FACILITIES, EQUIPMENT & OTHER RESOURCES

FACILITIES: Identify the facilities to be used at each performance site listed and, as appropriate, indicate their capacities, pertinent capabilities, relative proximity, and extent of availability to the project. Use "Other" to describe the facilities at any other performance sites listed and at sites for field studies. USE additional pages as necessary.

Laboratory:

Clinical:

Animal:

Computer:

Office: **ARCUS is expanding its capabilities to support NSF work by moving to a larger office building in March 2001. The building will be wired for advanced communications and Internet capability with a secure operating environment for the servers and other computer equipment necessary to sustain the work proposed in this cooperative**

Other: _____

MAJOR EQUIPMENT: List the most important items available for this project and, as appropriate identifying the location and pertinent capabilities of each.

OTHER RESOURCES: Provide any information describing the other resources available for the project. Identify support services such as consultant, secretarial, machine shop, and electronics shop, and the extent to which they will be available for the project. Include an explanation of any consortium/contractual arrangements with other organizations.

FACILITIES, EQUIPMENT & OTHER RESOURCES

Continuation Page:

OFFICE FACILITIES (continued):

agreement.

As the amount of work performed by ARCUS on behalf of the NSF has increased over the past six years, we have outgrown our infrastructure in terms of staffing and facilities. The move to the new facility in March 2001 will allow us to better meet current demands and provide the ability for moderate future expansion.